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**Crocodiles in the Sahara desert:
an update of distribution, habitats and population status
for conservation planning in Mauritania**

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Running title: Crocodiles in the Sahara

21 **Abstract**

22

23 *Background:* Relict populations of *Crocodylus niloticus* persist in Chad, Egypt and
24 Mauritania. Although crocodiles were widespread throughout the Sahara until early 20th
25 century, increased aridity combined with human persecution led to local extinction.
26 Knowledge on distribution, occupied habitats, population size and prey availability is scarce
27 in most populations. This study evaluates the status of Saharan crocodiles and provides new
28 data for Mauritania to assist conservation planning.

29 *Methodology/Principal Findings:* A series of surveys in Mauritania detected crocodile
30 presence in 78 localities dispersed across 10 river basins and most tended to be isolated
31 within river basins. Permanent *gueltas* and seasonal *tâmoûrts* were the most common
32 occupied habitats. Crocodile encounters ranged from one to more than 20 individuals, but in
33 most localities less than five crocodiles were observed. Larger numbers were observed after
34 the rainy season and during night sampling. Crocodiles were found dead in between water
35 points along dry river-beds suggesting the occurrence of dispersal.

36 *Conclusion/Significance:* Research priorities in Chad and Egypt should focus on quantifying
37 population size and pressures exerted on habitats. The present study increased in by 35%
38 the number of known crocodile localities in Mauritania. *Gueltas* are crucial for the persistence
39 of mountain populations. Oscillations in water availability throughout the year and the small
40 dimensions of *gueltas* affect biological traits, including activity and body size. Studies are
41 needed to understand adaptation traits of desert populations. Molecular analyses are needed
42 to quantify genetic variability, population sub-structuring and effective population size, and
43 detect the occurrence of gene flow. Monitoring is needed to detect demographical and
44 genetical trends in completely isolated populations. Crocodiles are apparently vulnerable
45 during dispersal events. Awareness campaigns focusing on the vulnerability and relict value
46 of crocodiles should be implemented. Classification of Mauritanian mountains as protected
47 areas should be prioritised.

48 **Introduction**

49

50 The Sahara is the largest desert in the world and it is characterised by the occurrence of
51 vast dune fields and featureless plains subjected to low precipitation levels and high
52 temperature ranges [1]. However, this apparently bare ecosystem has not always been like
53 this. Since the onset of the Sahara, at about 7 M.Y.A [2], its range has largely fluctuated
54 following closely periodical climatic oscillations. Several alternated phases of dry and humid
55 climates have occurred allowing the expansion and contraction of the desert areas,
56 respectively, through range shifts of the hyper-arid sand seas and featureless plains [3]. At
57 the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM, 18,000 yr), the Sahara was much larger and warmer than
58 today, but during the mid-Holocene (7,000 yr) it was almost absent due to the higher levels of
59 temperature and rainfall in comparison with the present day [4,5]. During this last humid
60 phase, the arid plains and sand seas were replaced by lakes, grasslands and open savannas
61 in many low altitude sites, and temperate xerophytic woods and warm mixed forests covered
62 mountains [6-8].

63 Palaeogeological events and climatic shifts constitute driving factors of current species
64 distribution and diversity patterns in the Sahara. The progressive coolness that followed the
65 arid LGM allowed “humid” species of Mediterranean and sub-Saharan affinity to spread over
66 the shrunken Sahara and the mild climatic conditions of the mid-Holocene made available
67 suitable aquatic environments for many nowadays-extinct fauna, such elephants, giraffes or
68 hippopotamus [9,10]. But after the Holocene, a new period of increased aridity began, that
69 gradually dried the savannah-like ecosystems, and culminated with the revitalization of the
70 Sahara. The disappearance of most aquatic habitats and productive savannas induced local
71 extinction of almost all humidity-dependent species in the lower altitude areas and pushed
72 populations to peripheral wetter regions [9,10].

73 Remarkably, relict populations have persisted in mountains where suitable climatic
74 conditions endured. Saharan mountains constitute refugia for species of Mediterranean
75 affinity, such as the olive tree (*Olea laperrini*) and the false smooth snake (*Macroprotodon*

76 *cucullatus*), and of sub-Saharan affinity, like the savannah toad (*Amietophrynus xeros*) and
77 the Guinea baboon (*Papio papio*) [11-13]. Although surrounded by inhospitable desert areas,
78 these species persist in mountain lagoons, dune lakes and high altitude mountain peaks. The
79 isolation and small size of these habitats renders many populations vulnerable to extinction
80 by stochastic events, loss of genetic diversity and demographic fluctuations [14-16]. Also,
81 these biodiversity hotspots are currently under high vulnerability to climate changes [authors,
82 unpub. data] and recent increased drought has been responsible for the local extinction of
83 fish populations [17].

84 The Nile crocodile (*Crocodylus niloticus*) is one of the species occurring in the Sahara
85 that experienced historical range contractions and is currently vulnerable to population
86 isolation. Crocodiles were widespread throughout the Sahara at least from the mid-Holocene
87 up to Roman times (Figure 1), and numerous fossil records and rock engravings depicting
88 crocodiles are known from this period [reviewed by 18]. The increased aridity combined with
89 human persecution has probably led to the extinction of numerous populations. By the turn of
90 19th century, the Saharan historical exploratory missions reported their presence in the
91 Algerian mountains of Tassili 'n'Ajjer [reviewed by 18], and in the 1930s, crocodiles were also
92 found in southern Mauritanian mountains and the Ennedi massif of eastern Chad [19-22]
93 (Figure 1). But soon researchers found that populations were very small and declining due to
94 increasing human pressure [19,23,24]. From the beginning of the 20th century until the
95 1960s, crocodile populations were extinct from the Chott El Djerid (Tunisia), the Hoggar and
96 Tassili 'n'Ajjer mountains (Algeria) and the lower Drâa river (Morocco) [reviewed by 18].
97 Crocodiles were present at Ihérir-Imihrou and Tedjoujelt, Tassili n'Ajjer, until the 1920s
98 [reviewed by 18], and an inhabitant from Ihérir village stated that he killed one specimen in
99 1946 [25]. Populations were also suggested to occur at I-n-Houter, Hoggar, and inquiries to
100 locals reported their presence until the 1950s [18,25]. Interestingly, inquiries stated the
101 presence of crocodiles in 1984 at lake I-n-Tawinast, Immidir mountains [25]. Nevertheless,
102 several missions held later were unable to detect the presence of crocodiles in any of these
103 localities and the species is considered to be locally extinct [18].

104 In Mauritania, crocodiles were reported in the Tagant [26], but the first revision on the
105 status of Saharan populations considered Mauritanian crocodiles to be nearly extinct, with
106 populations probably remaining in the Assaba and Affolé mountains of southern Mauritania,
107 and concluded that Saharan crocodile populations were virtually extinct [18]. Several
108 scientific expeditions to Mauritania were developed from 2000 onwards [27-31] which
109 reported the presence of crocodiles in three southern Mauritania massifs: Tagant, Assaba
110 and Affolé (Figure 1). Populations are best known in the Gabbou basin, on the northern face
111 of the Tagant mountains, where they are present in 26 isolated localities [29,31]. But outside
112 this river basin, knowledge on distribution is scarce. In the Affolé, crocodiles are known from
113 four localities [27,28], and in the Assaba, references date from before the 1970s [18,32-34].
114 In the Tagant, crocodiles are mostly found in two major habitat types [29-31]: 1) rocky pools,
115 locally known as *guelta*, generally located upstream of narrow valleys at the base of the
116 mountains. In many cases water is only available during the rainy season (July to
117 September), when torrential waterfalls fill up the pools. The size of gueltas varies according
118 to the geomorphology of mountain slopes but generally are small, ranging between 0.001 ha
119 and 1.0 ha; and 2) floodplains, locally known as *tâmoûrt*, located on the foothills of the
120 mountains, which are larger in size and reach frequently more than 1,000 ha. Nevertheless,
121 water is usually shallow and tâmoûrts are mostly arid during the dry season (October to
122 June), thus crocodiles are forced to find shelter in nearby rock outcrops during this period
123 [27,30]. Despite the recognized importance of gueltas and tâmoûrts for the persistence of
124 populations in the Tagant, little is known about occupied habitats in the Affolé and Assaba
125 where crocodiles have been suggested to use distinct habitats, such as rivers (locally known
126 as *oued*), lakes and dams [29,32].

127 Crocodile populations in Mauritania are fragmented and many are constituted by a small
128 number of individuals [27,29-31,35]. Estimates are mostly restricted to the Tagant, where
129 one to three individuals were mentioned in small sized gueltas [31] and one to eight
130 individuals in eight gueltas of the Krâa Naga river [29]. Larger numbers, 30 to 40 individuals,
131 were mentioned to be present in tâmoûrts bordering Mali and Senegal [30]. Crocodiles have

132 been reported to prey mostly upon fishes, birds, locust, frogs, and young domestic goats and
133 sheep, and the Nile monitor (*Varanus niloticus*) has been suggested to be a predator of
134 crocodile eggs and a prey for adult crocodiles, indicating a possible predator-prey
135 relationship [27,30,36]. During the rainy season, water connections are established between
136 many gueltas and tâmoûrts which might allow dispersal between populations through
137 temporarily suitable corridors. In fact, movements of crocodiles during rainy season were
138 recently suggested to occur [30,31], but evidence remain flimsy and it is unknown if actual
139 gene flow occurs between populations. Most likely, loss of genetic diversity and inbreeding
140 depression due to reproductive isolation are expected to threaten these populations [e.g. 37].

141 This study aims to evaluate the status of crocodiles in the Sahara and for Mauritania, in
142 particular, it is aimed to update the distribution, characterise occupied habitats, provide local
143 counts of crocodiles, and assess possible dispersal events. The results of this study are
144 intended to increase the knowledge about distribution and occupied habitats by crocodiles in
145 the Sahara, and to assist conservation planning in Mauritania, particularly to provide
146 additional data for the recent listing of the “Gabbou basin” in the Ramsar Convention [38].

147

148 **Methods**

149 Ethics statement: Fieldwork in Mauritania developed with permission from the Ministère
150 Délégué auprès du Premier Ministre, Chargé de l'Environnement. Parc National du Banc
151 d'Arguin, Nouakchott (Permit: 460/MDE/PNBA). There are no animal husbandry,
152 experimentation and care/welfare concerns.

153

154 **Study area in Mauritania**

155 The study area encompasses the mountains of Tagant, Assaba and Affolé, in southern
156 Mauritania. Altitude ranges from 9 m on the Senegal river valley up to 625 m in the Tagant.
157 There is a cool, dry season from November to February and a hot, dry season from March to
158 June [39]. Variation in annual average temperature is relatively small and tends to follow the

159 altitudinal gradient [40]. Rain falls in a single wet season from July to October, with most
160 precipitation in August and September [39]. There is a marked north-south gradient in annual
161 precipitation, from 98 mm in the northern desert areas to 884 mm in the extreme southern
162 region of the study area [40].

163 Most of the study area is covered by open and sparse grasslands (49.3%; [41]) with
164 vegetation dominated by *Acacia ehrenbergiana*, *Acacia tortilis*, *Balanites aegyptiaca* and
165 associated species [31]. Stony and sandy desert with dunes (24.7%), present only in the
166 northern region, and croplands (17.3%), present only in the southern region, complete the
167 most representative land cover types of the study area [41].

168

169 Fieldwork in Mauritania

170 Two field missions were developed in 2008 (10 October to 18 November) and 2009 (31
171 March to 5 May), following previous short-timed visits in 2003 (21 to 25 November) and 2007
172 (9 to 16 December), totalling 109 days of fieldwork. A total of 102 localities (water points)
173 were visited, of which 19 were visited in two or more occasions. Each visited locality was
174 sampled for the presence of crocodiles by four persons (2008 and 2009 only) using a
175 combination of distinct methodologies: 1) visual inspection of water from elevated points
176 using binoculars and a telescope; 2) search of crocodile signs in shorelines, including faeces,
177 footprints, tracks or burrows excavated in compact-sandy terrain; 3) inspection of rock
178 crevices for hidden crocodiles; 4) night sampling of water and margins with lamps in 26
179 localities; and 5) inquiries to locals about the presence of crocodiles and location of dead
180 crocodiles. The number of crocodiles present at each locality was quantified, distinguishing
181 between day and night periods. Sampling of tâmoûrts was limited by their frequent large
182 dimensions and most likely the number of crocodiles observed represents a small fraction of
183 the population.

184 Crocodiles found dead were measured, photographed and the probable cause of death
185 was estimated. In some cases locals informed us that the crocodile had been deliberately
186 killed and clear beating marks were usually found in the head. Inquires were also used to

187 complement information about annual water availability, permanent or seasonal, and the
188 month when locality dries. To identify dispersal events, vehicle-based surveys were
189 conducted whenever possible along the river-beds between localities with known presence of
190 crocodiles. Riverbeds were in many occasions the main overland route between localities,
191 which facilitated sampling and inquiries to locals. Occurrence of dispersal was considered
192 when dead crocodiles were found along the dry river-beds in between water localities. The
193 coordinates of localities with crocodiles and crocodiles found dead outside water points were
194 gathered from a Global Positioning System (GPS).

195

196 Analytical methods

197 Localities with presence of crocodiles were collected from bibliographic references,
198 including for the Saharan Holocene [9,18,32,43-55], for the Sahara excluding Mauritania
199 [18,22,23,25,53,56-61], and for Mauritania only [9,18,20,26-29,31-33,35,39,42,44,45,62].
200 These included localities with geographic coordinates or with clear geographic designations
201 from which it was possible to gather coordinates from topographical maps (1:200,000 from
202 Institut Géographique National, IGN). Localities were displayed in the Geographical
203 Information System (GIS) ArcGIS 9.3 [63] on the WGS84 datum. Locality names used in this
204 study follow the toponymies established in the IGN maps.

205 Status of populations in Mauritania was ranked in four categories: 1) present, when
206 crocodiles were observed during field missions, when faeces or footprints were found, or
207 when recent bibliographic references (after year 2000) reported presence but field missions
208 did not sampled these localities; 2) possible, when locals reported presence of crocodiles in
209 apparently suitable habitats but individuals or their signs were not observed; 3) not
210 confirmed, when localities referenced recently in bibliography (after year 2000) with presence
211 were sampled during field missions but individuals or their signs were not observed; 4)
212 extinct, when inquiries to locals and bibliographic references reported the extinction of
213 crocodiles and field missions also did not found evidences for their presence.

214

215 **Results**

216

217 Populations of the Nile crocodile in the Sahara are currently known from three countries,
218 Chad, Egypt and Mauritania (Figure 1). An appreciation on the status of populations and
219 conservation issues affecting habitats are given below. Summary data on Saharan localities
220 (excluding extant populations in Mauritania) are given in Table 1.

221

222 **Chad**

223 Populations of crocodiles in Chad are best known from Guelta Archei in the eastern
224 Ennedi mountains, where several individuals have been reported since the 1930s (Figure 1)
225 [18,22,57,61,64]. There are no quantifications of population size, but crocodiles were stated
226 to occur in large numbers in the 1950s [reviewed by 22]. Two specimens were photographed
227 in the 1990s [22] and another one in 2007 [61]. Crocodiles have been also suggested to
228 occur at gueltas Oudougeï and Tottous [reviewed by 18], but presence lack confirmation due
229 to the regional conflicts that hamper the access to the Tibesti mountains.

230

231 **Egypt**

232 Crocodiles were abundant in the Nile delta up to the 1800s, but by the beginning of the
233 20th century they became largely restricted to the Nile south of Aswan and probably went
234 extinct during the 1960s (Figure 1) [53]. After the completion of the High Dam and the filling
235 of Lake Nasser in the late 1960s, suitable habitats were created and crocodiles returned [53].
236 Colonisation probably occurred with dispersal individuals arriving from populations in The
237 Sudan. Population size is estimated to be considerably less than 5,000 breeding adults [53],
238 and recent surveys counted an average of 71.5 crocodiles per 100 km of shoreline sampled
239 [65]. Conflicts with growing human activities in the region are increasing, particularly with
240 fishers, and crocodiles are locally hunted for pet trade and skins [53,65].

241

242 Mauritania

243 Field missions and bibliographic references identified 78 crocodile localities in Mauritania
244 (Figures 2 and 3; Table 2). Of these, crocodiles were found to be present and possibly
245 present in 60 and 11 localities, respectively, whereas their presence was not confirmed in
246 four previously known localities, and confirmed as extinct from three localities. Presence was
247 for the first time reported in 27 localities, meaning that this study increased in 35% the
248 number of known localities with crocodiles in Mauritania.

249 Excluding localities where crocodiles were not confirmed or extinct, gueltas and tâmoûrts
250 were the most common habitats where individuals were found (40.8% and 26.8%,
251 respectively), but presence was detected also in oueds (9.9%), sources (8.5%), lakes (8.5%)
252 and dams (5.6%) (Figures 4 and 5). Crocodiles were observed in 19 permanent gueltas
253 (73% of gueltas surveyed) and 17 seasonal tâmoûrts (90% of tâmoûrts surveyed).

254 The total number of crocodiles observed was 178, including yearlings to adults (Figure 6).
255 The number of observations ranged from one to more than 20 individuals in 33 sampled
256 localities. The smallest population was the single adult present in guelta El Khedia (Figure
257 6C). In most localities, less than five crocodiles were observed (N=17) and seven of these
258 localities corresponded to gueltas. Most localities where more than 10 crocodiles were
259 observed had permanent water (N=5) and all of these corresponded to gueltas.

260 Four localities along the Krâa Naga oued (gueltas Amzouzef, Ch'Bayer, Matmâta, and
261 Tartêga) were sampled in the period 2000-2002 [29] and the average (\pm standard deviation)
262 number of crocodiles detected was 2.8 ± 3.5 . This study sampled these localities in the period
263 2008-2009 and the number of individuals observed was 6.5 ± 3.1 .

264 A larger number of crocodiles were observed after the rainy season in comparison with
265 the dry season. In localities with crocodiles sampled in late 2008 (N=20), an average of 5.9
266 individuals were observed, whereas in localities sampled in early 2009 (N=13), an average of
267 3.5 crocodiles were observed. Also, in localities sampled during daylight and at night (N=20),
268 more crocodiles were observed on average at night (6.1 ± 5.3) than during daylight (2.7 ± 4.6).

269 A total of 10 crocodiles were found dead, of which five had been killed by locals, two died
270 from apparently natural reasons and three by unknown reasons (only bone remains were
271 found after digging). Seven of these crocodiles were found in between water points along the
272 dry river-bed and were considered to be dispersing (Figure 6B and 6F). All dispersing
273 individuals found were sub-adults and adults with body size larger than 1.20 m. Five
274 dispersing crocodiles were found along the Krâa Naga oued (Gabbou basin, Tagant) where
275 gueltas are usually found at relative short distances (on average less than 4 km).

276 The 78 localities are dispersed across 10 river basins and most tended to be isolated
277 within river basins (Figure 2). Summary data on localities, population status, and date of last
278 observation are given in Table 2. Detailed data on localities, crocodile observations,
279 population status, and conservation issues affecting habitats in Mauritania are given in
280 supporting material S1.

281

282 **Discussion**

283

284 Nile crocodiles occur in the Sahara desert in fragmented populations throughout several
285 mountains. Although the mechanisms explaining the presence of crocodiles in the Sahara
286 are well understood [e.g. 10], in reality there is paucity of knowledge about distribution,
287 demography, ecology, and conservation status of populations. Research priorities in Chad
288 and Egypt should focus on studies quantifying population size and pressures exerted on
289 habitats in the population present in guelta Archei and Lake Nasser [e.g. 65]. Field surveys
290 are also needed in the Tibesti where the presence of crocodiles is uncertain [57]. The
291 remoteness and isolation character of these mountains might have assured the persistence
292 of crocodiles. Fine-scaled remote sensing techniques might be applied prior to fieldwork in
293 order to identify suitable water localities for the occurrence of crocodiles [66-68].

294 The present study increased in by 35% the number of known crocodile localities in
295 Mauritania. Presence was confirmed in 60 localities and another 11 were identified as of
296 possible presence. The increase in known localities is probably related to previous lack of

297 sampling and cryptic behaviour of crocodiles. The remote character of southern Mauritanian
298 mountains, associated to with logistical fieldwork constraints, has prevented detailed
299 sampling. Also, crocodiles were found spending large portions of time hidden inside caves or
300 burrows [27,30,31], further hampering their detection (e.g. Figure 6E). Thus, it is likely that
301 increased sampling will detect more populations. The southern Gorgol el Abiod, Gorgol el
302 Akhdar, Garfa and Karakoro basins should be further surveyed as suitable areas may be
303 present. Sampling should also be aimed to extreme south-eastern Mauritania, where besides
304 lake Dendaré (locality 78), no other localities are known, but water availability (e.g.
305 Mahmoûdé lake) may allow crocodile presence. Assessment of population status along the
306 Senegal river is also needed, where accidental death in fishnets and direct harvesting may
307 have severely reduced populations and restricted crocodiles to local suitable areas, such as
308 the National Parks of Diawling (Mauritania) and Djoudj (Senegal) [28,35,69]. While local
309 beliefs of the Moor ethnic group protect mountain-ranging crocodiles [27,28,30], the southern
310 Mauritania ethnic groups hunts them for skin, organs and meat, along the Senegal river and
311 major tributaries [28,36]. The increasing human pressure is also the most likely responsible
312 for the extinction of the Slender-snouted crocodile (*Crocodylus cataphractus*), which was
313 reported along the Senegal river [36,70], but currently is considered extinct [28].

314 Crocodiles were mostly found in gueltas and tâmoûrts, which is probably related to their
315 higher abundance in comparison to other water habitats. Gueltas are apparently crucial for
316 the persistence of crocodiles in mountains, as already emphasised for other vertebrates with
317 isolated populations [15-17]. Population size is probably small (on average less than five
318 individuals were observed at each locality), particularly at gueltas, which stresses the
319 vulnerability of these habitats to threat factors. After the severe droughts of the 1970s
320 [71,72], there were large human movements and settlement around water localities [30].
321 Currently, several gueltas are overexploited by herdsman, producing water-shortage during
322 the dry season, faecal contamination by domestic animals, and increased activities for
323 excavating pools or pumping water [31]. Furthermore, several small-sized gueltas were
324 strongly disturbed by drinking cattle during daylight (Figure 4D). Although crocodiles tend to

325 be more active at night [73], increased human activities during daylight force individuals in
326 small-sized gueltas to remain hidden, while at night they are able to explore the surroundings
327 of lagoons. Local studies should be conducted to quantify pressures and threat risks
328 affecting crocodile populations.

329 Oscillations in water availability throughout the year and the relatively small dimensions
330 of gueltas have dramatic consequences in the activity and ecology of populations. During the
331 dry season, individuals are forced to aestivate [73]. In gueltas, they find shelter between the
332 rock boulders of the rocky slopes, as observed in guelta Legleyta (Figure 6E), while in
333 tâmoûrts, they burying themselves below the mud surface or migrate to nearby rock
334 outcrops, as observed in tâmoûrt Bougâri [27,28,30]. Apparently, crocodile presence is more
335 frequent in tâmoûrts with available rock outcrops within a 5 km perimeter [28]. Activity is
336 concentrated in the period when water is available and more crocodiles were observed after
337 the rainy season than during the dry season. Apparently, mountain populations of crocodiles
338 have the feeding, growth and reproductive period restricted to just about 10 weeks per year
339 (or even less at some localities). During the rainy season and the following weeks, prey
340 availability may increase dramatically, as observed at Chegg el Mâleh (Figure 6H): in
341 November, there were hundreds of active amphibians (*Hoplobatrachus occipitalis*), while in
342 December, no amphibians were detected and the tâmoûrt was dry, suggesting that
343 crocodiles should feed only during the active period of amphibians. The relatively short
344 feeding period and available prey of small size, mostly fishes and amphibians, probably
345 affects growth rates and reduces maximum body size [30,73]. All crocodiles observed were
346 less than 3 m long, and the vast majority were less than 2 m (Figure 6G). The largest
347 crocodiles were observed in guelta Tartêga, which has permanent water and is one of the
348 biggest gueltas of Mauritania (Figure 4A). Although hatchlings or nests were not found,
349 yearling crocodiles were observed at Matmâta and sub-adults were observed in several
350 localities (Figure 6A and 6D), suggesting that reproduction occurs in isolated populations.
351 Demographical, behavioural and thermoregulatory studies should be conducted to
352 understand adaptation traits of these populations to extreme environmental conditions.

353 Dead crocodiles were found between water points along dry river-beds, suggesting the
354 occurrence of dispersal (Figures 6B and 6F). Movement of crocodiles during the rainy
355 season along temporary water connections have been suggested to occur in mountain
356 populations. A displacement of a crocodile of 2 km over dunes has been reported [30] and
357 potential extinctions in small gueltas, with 1 to 3 individuals, have been suggested that could
358 be compensated by the arrival of animals moving along river beds [31]. Possible population
359 connectivity could occur along the Krâa Naga and upper Karakoro basins, where there are
360 several gueltas and tâmoûrts, respectively, located at relatively short distances (e.g.
361 Ch'Bayer and Rh' Zembou in the former, and Taghtâfet, Jaraaziza, Tâmcchekket in the latter).
362 Also, tâmoûrt Djouk is of special relevance given that it may assure connectivity between
363 populations located in the Tagant and Assaba mountains. Thus, it can be hypothesized that
364 Mauritanian crocodiles form a metapopulation, where loss of genetical diversity in lagoons
365 could be attenuated by the occasional migration of individuals with associated gene flow.
366 Furthermore, dispersal from mountain lagoons to the Senegal river may also occur through
367 the Gorgol and Garfa rivers but supporting evidences are needed. Use of molecular markers
368 is necessary to quantify genetic variability, population sub-structuring and effective
369 population size, and detect the occurrence of gene flow.

370 The present study identified localities completely isolated without any possibility of
371 rescuing-effects [74]. This is the case of source Oumm Icheglâne and guelta Legleyta, which
372 are isolated within the Assaba mountains. The most dramatic case occurs at guelta El
373 Khedia (locality 29; Figure 3 and 6C), where a single adult is the remaining exemplar from a
374 larger population [review by 18] and the nearest population is relatively distant (37 km).
375 Isolation by distance apparently prevents dispersal between water localities. For instance,
376 guelta Mendjoura had crocodiles until severe droughts in the 1970s induced local extinction.
377 The closest locality with crocodiles, Boû blei'îne (Figure 5B), is at over 60 km and the
378 connecting oued is totally covered by dunes. Thus, although the guelta currently presents
379 reasonable water levels and prey is available, large distances and unsuitable habitats
380 apparently hamper colonisation. Monitoring of effectively-isolated populations is needed to

381 detect demographical and genetical trends. Introduction of specimens from nearby relatively
382 dense populations should be considered for El Khedia.

383 The isolation and vulnerability of mountain populations apparently induces behavioural
384 shifts in aggressiveness patterns of crocodiles. Individuals are extremely shy and plunge into
385 water at the first sign of human disturbance. Interestingly, this behaviour was also reported
386 for the extinct Algerian populations [24]. In Mauritania, inquiries did not indicate crocodile
387 attacks to humans and, as previously observed by Shine et al. [27], locals swim and wash in
388 gueltas with crocodiles. Even so, when more than one lagoon was available, humans used
389 preferentially the lower ones and crocodiles were more numerous in the upper ones.
390 Although local beliefs protect crocodiles [27,28,30], these are apparently killed whenever
391 found far from the gueltas, probably during dispersal events. Local public awareness
392 campaigns focusing on the vulnerability and relict value of crocodile populations should be
393 implemented.

394 Climate change scenarios for the region predict significant warming and rainfall decrease
395 [75,76], which are expected to increase population isolation and local extinction [authors,
396 unpub. data]. Multi-scale conservation strategies are needed to protect populations and
397 mitigate climate change effects [77]. Classification of Mauritanian mountains as protected
398 areas should be prioritised, as these should contribute to minimise human induced land
399 transformation and habitat loss [78], which are also important threats to local biodiversity.

400

401 **Supporting Information**

402 Supporting material S1 Detailed data on localities, crocodile observations, population status,
403 and conservation issues affecting habitats in Mauritania.

404

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410

411 **Author contributions**

412 Conceived and designed the experiments: JCB. Performed the experiments: JCB, FMF, PS,
413 NS, PT. Analyzed the data: JCB, FMF, NS, PT. Contributed reagents/materials/analysis
414 tools: JCB, FMF, PS, NS, PT. Wrote the paper: JCB, FMF, PS, NS, PT.

415

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600

601 **Figure 1. Distribution of crocodiles in North Africa.** Dots represent localities where
602 crocodiles are currently present (present), where presence is possible but needs
603 confirmation (possible), where crocodiles were extinct in the 20th century (extinct) or where
604 crocodiles were present during the Holocene. Line represents the current northern limit of
605 the range of continuous populations. Extinction localities georeferenced from
606 [18,23,25,56,58-60]. Holocene localities georeferenced from [9,18,32,43-55]. Possible and
607 present localities from outside Mauritania georeferenced from [18,22,53,57,61,64].

608

609 **Figure 2. Distribution of crocodile localities along major river basins of southern**
610 **Mauritania.** Dots represent localities where crocodiles are currently present (present), where
611 presence is possible but needs confirmation (possible), where crocodiles were reported to be
612 present but this study did not confirmed their presence (not confirmed) or where crocodiles
613 went extinct (extinct). Easternmost known locality in Mauritania (locality 78) is only
614 represented in small inset. Numbers refer to localities described in Table 2. Localities for
615 Gabbou basin are shown in detail in Figure 3. Background is a composite Landsat image
616 depicting land-cover.

617

618 **Figure 3. Distribution of crocodile localities along the Gabbou river basin on Tagant**
619 **mountains.** Dots represent localities where crocodiles are currently present (present), where
620 crocodiles were reported to be present but this study did not confirmed their presence (not
621 confirmed) or where crocodiles were found dead (found dead). Numbers refer to localities
622 described in Table 2. Names represent major seasonal water lines flowing to the Gabbou
623 lake. Background is a composite Landsat image depicting land-cover.

624

625 **Figure 4. Examples of gueltas with presence of Nile crocodiles in Mauritania.** A.
626 Tartêga; B. El Khedia; C. Garaouel; D. Oumm el Mhâr.

627

628 **Figure 5. Examples of oueds, lakes and tâmoûrts with presence of Nile crocodiles in**
629 **Mauritania.** A. oued Fougoussas; B. lake Boû bleiîne; C. tâmoûrt Taghtâfet; D. tâmoûrt
630 Bougâri.

631

632 **Figure 6. Examples of Nile crocodiles from Mauritania.** A. juveniles at guelta Matmâta; B.
633 adult killed at Dar-Salam village, near guelta Matmâta; C. the single adult at guelta El
634 Khedia; D. sub-adult at guelta Garaouel; E. two adults hidden in a cave at 8 m depth in
635 guelta Legleyta; F. adult killed near tâmoûrt Taghtâfet; G. basking adults at guelta
636 Metraoucha; H. sub-adult inside a spring-fed water trough at Chegg el Mâleh surrounded by
637 hundreds of frogs (*Hoplobatrachus occipitalis*).